

Report on Deliverable 7.1.

Project Information

Project title: Dynamo Project

Grant agreement ID: 101046489

Programme: HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN

Coordinated by: Universitat Jaume I, Spain

Project start date: 1 March 2022 **Project end date:** 28 February 2026

Deliverable Information

Deliverable title: WP7 - D7.1: Project website including main information, deliverables, outputs, results, etc. and social media profiles of the project.

Delivery date: 30 April 2022

Dissemination level: Public — fully open.

Comment: The deliverable has been submitted as planned in the Grant Agreement.

Detailed description of the deliverable:

Project website

First of all, the website domain has been bought as www.dynamo-project.eu, and it will be maintained after the end of the project in order to maximise the impact. The EU emblem and the disclaimer have been applied as mention in the ARTICLE 17 — COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY of the General Model Grant Agreement EIC Accelerator Contract, Version 1.0 (01 June 2021). Moreover, the project's corporate visual identity (logo) has been designed to maintain consistency across all communication channels.

Regarding the structure of the website, in the menu can be found the home page entitled **About the project** with the identifying information of the project, and the abstract explaining what the objectives, the innovation and the results expected. This description has been meticulously thought through applying communication messages to be understood by a wide audience. Other specific sections such as results are more address to a scientific or technical audience (dissemination). The second section that can be found is the **Partnership**, where it is explained the entities that are participating as coordinator, partners and affiliated entities. In order to make it more visual a map has been integrated together with a short description of each of them. In the same section, the Advisory Board and the Associated Partners have been also described as they are part of the team and they will give input to the project. Next section is the **Results**, there is a list with all the work packages and deliverables expected to submit during the four years of the project and indicating those that will be public, and therefore, that will be available for downloading. **Blog and news** are the section where the latest updates will be posted in the form of press releases, newsletters, videos and brochures. Finally, in the section **Contact** appears a contact form to let the audience to get in contact with the project and their members. All the social media profiles and linked to the website, in the case of Twitter as a feed.

Social media profiles

According to what was stated in the Dynamo form, the Twitter ([@DynamoProjectEU](https://twitter.com/DynamoProjectEU)), [Linkedin](#), and [Youtube](#) accounts have been created with fully identity of the project. Different strategies are being applied to each channel in order to engage many audiences.